

Towards a Political Understanding of Christianity: The Theological Turn in Theory and Terry Eagleton

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Abstract

In this paper, we shall examine the role played by Terry Eagleton (who is arguably the most famous literary and cultural theorist of the contemporary Anglophone world) within the so-called theological turn in critical theory which is heralded by the engagement of some of the most important critical theorists of contemporary times with Christian theology in recent times. The significance of the Christian theology in providing an ethical critique of a de-ideologised, de-politicised, individualistic liberal social order of today derived from Enlightenment can be explored in our survey of Eagleton's theological works, enabling us to appreciate the materialist and revolutionary-transformative potential of Christianity (particularly the Thomist school) in offering us a catholic methodology of reading.

The regular interactions between Western Marxism and Christianity are quite old by now. Roland Boer has produced a massive, three-volume study of these crossroads between Marxism and Christianity (respectively titled *Criticism of Heaven*, *Criticism of Religion* and *Criticism of Theology*). Terry Eagleton himself, who was a devout Catholic in his childhood, being an altar boy in a Catholic seminary, came to be associated with a radical left Catholic group named *Slant* in the Cambridge University during his student days (in the 1960s) which brought out an eponymous journal. During his early critical career, Eagleton authored a few theological works as well. But since then, 1970 onwards, his works were all strictly secular in nature. The scenario changes with the publication of *After Theory* and *Sweet Violence* in 2003, both of which advocate the use of a political-theological method in cultural analysis. Since then, Eagleton's commentaries (on the otherwise non-theological subject matters also, as he continues to publish on a wide array of literary and cultural topics) have remained committed to a basic theological framework of analysis.

While the theological turn in Eagleton's critical career closely corresponds to the engagement with Christian theology in the works of a number of contemporary radical thinkers like Slavoj Žižek, Alain Badiou and Giorgio Agamben, in this paper we shall analyse and explore the implications of Eagleton's recent theological works. Eagleton's *After Theory* was the first manifesto for a post-Enlightenment, post-secular methodology which now must replace the standard fare of cultural theory which

has been shamefaced about morality and metaphysics, embarrassed about love, biology, religion and revolution, largely silent about evil, reticent about death and suffering, dogmatic about essences, universals and foundations, and superficial about truth, objectivity and disinterestedness. This, on any estimate, is rather a large slice of human experience to fall down on. It is also, as we have suggested before, rather an awkward moment in history to find oneself with little or nothing to say about such fundamental questions. Let us see if we can

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begin to remedy these deficiencies by addressing these issues in a different light. (101-102)

That different light is a theological methodology having some definite political implications, which Eagleton forwards in his *Sweet Violence* (2003) and later again in *Holy Terror* (2005). Both of these works deal with tragedy. While appraising of this crucial and strategic place of tragedy in his political theology, Eagleton observes in a conversational tone:

Tragedy allowed me to get all sorts of things off my chest. Taken together with works like *Holy Terror* which I actually like more than *Sweet Violence*, though I don't think it's as substantial I was able to articulate what I think was becoming an increasingly coherent world-view. By this point I had overcome a certain materialist coyness and was able to talk openly about certain metaphysical or theological matters that concerned me; and in this I was greatly inspired by the theological upfrontness of atheists like Badiou, Agamben and Zizek. I mean, if they could do it, couldn't a former altar boy do it too? (*Task of the Critic* 277)

Eagleton's trajectory out of the confines of secular cultural theory into the domain of theological is surely at odds with the conventional discourses of left wing radicalism and he is aware of this antagonism which exists between left politics and theology: "The left is at home with imperial power and guerilla warfare, but embarrassed on the whole by the thought of death, evil, sacrifice or the sublime," but paradoxically "the politics implicit in this rather exotic talk of Satan and Dionysus, scapegoat and demons, are more, not less radical than much that is to be found in the more orthodox discourses of leftism today" (*Holy Terror* vi). Eagleton's suggestion is obvious, as we can ourselves see that the materialism practised by conventional left criticism is often crude, mechanistic, reductive, vulgar and as such is tone-deaf to the rich political matrix of the historical development of theology down the ages.

What really causes this renewal of critical interest in Christian theology is a question that must remain open. This is most likely an overdetermined phenomenon (using the term in the Althusserian sense), but surely this theological turn is a radical political move against the dominant trends of global capitalism, liberalisation, liberalism, and an amnesiac, individualised social order based on contract rather than on kinship and fraternity. All the theological critiques have come from radical theorists with known and proven track records of political activism: Badiou, Zizek and Eagleton and Agamben all belong to the left spectrum of intelligentsia beyond any doubt. But they all are aware of the shortcoming of the conventional, secular political criticism and want to explore Christianity in search of a holistic critique of the human condition. We can have a cursory glance at the ventures of three major critical theorists other than Eagleton in this regard. In 2003 Alain Badiou publishes his ontotheological study of St Paul and the event of the foundation of Christianity in his *St Paul: The Foundation of Universalism*. After having discussed the metaphysical dimensions of the *homo sacer* (the sacred as well as the cursed man) in a number of his works, in 2007 Giorgio Agamben publishes his critique of what he terms the capitalist travesty of theological *oikonomia* (economy) in *The*

Kingdom and the Glory: For a Theological Genealogy of Economy and Government. Žižek in his 2003 study *The Puppet and the Dwarf: The Perverse Core of Christianity* celebrates the proverbial dwarf of theology controlling the puppet of history. In other words he reveals theology to be the driving force behind the material workings of history.

These three thinkers are atheistic, though, in the loose sense that they do not believe in God. And thus their theological critiques can qualify as negative theology: theology which revolves around a negation or a vacuum (un)known as God. Here Eagleton's contribution towards the theological turn demands special attention from us, because Eagleton is writing from a Catholic, theistic perspective (where he is heavily indebted to Dominican theologian Fr Herbert McCabe who exerts a deep influence on Eagleton) in his theological studies which include *After Theory* and *Sweet Violence* (both in 2003), *Holy Terror* (2005), *Jesus Christ: The Gospels* and *The Meaning of Life* (both in 2007), *Reason, Faith and Revolution: Reflections on the God Debate* (2009) and *On Evil* (2010).

Eagleton's overt emphasis on the figure of Christ who unifies the Greek tragic motif of the *pharmakos* (sacrificial scapegoat) with the biblical figure of the *anawim* (the wretched of the earth) in the theological studies is matched by Eagleton's Thomistic and Aristotelian emphasis on God as love, and the Christian project of transformation through love, which has a glorious pointlessness about it; and in that aspect it runs parallel to evil, which too is pointless. The sublime metaphysics of death leads Eagleton into the quest for the meaning of life, which he finds in the Aristotelian ethics (which of course undergo a Thomistic adaptation as they are made to enter the Christian project of redemption). This is an ethical model based on love, mutually enriching, commonly and reciprocally shared. And this love is not utilitarian; Eagleton often compares the love of God for the created beings with the gratuitous work of an artist, who creates for the sheer pleasure involved in the act of creation alone. Eagleton also offers a synthesis of theology and Lacanian psychoanalysis in describing God as the Lacanian Real, that which lies beyond the realm of the Symbolic. The painful limitedness and fallenness of the human condition can be salvaged on the plane of a community based on love. Such a model of collective, intersubjective ethics becomes inseparable from revolutionary politics in Eagleton's theological works.

Eagleton ultimately comes up with a catholic/holistic theory of the human condition which he calls tragic humanism, which he posits against the Enlightenment-derived liberal humanism that dominates Western Modernity, attacking the representative figure of liberal humanism in the caricature called Ditchkins (a fictional combination of noted secular-liberal-rationalist-atheist thinkers Richard Dawkins and Christopher Hitchens) in *Reason, Faith and Revolution*. He exposes the vulgar, mechanistic materialism inherent in the so-called 'new atheism' of Dawkins and Hitchens (deriving from Enlightenment rationalism), and opposes the triumphalist doctrine of progress on the ground that it is shallow, narrow, callous and amnesiac. Contrary to the naive optimism of contemporary liberal humanism, Eagleton's project of tragic humanism is keenly aware of the frailties of a 'fallen' human subject, and celebrates a

community based on mutual sacrifice and gratuitous love as a revolutionary method for redeeming the human condition. The exciting achievements of Eagleton's theological studies can be multi-faceted. On one hand, Eagleton provides us with a revolutionary-ethical method for re-assessing the texts from the past, including the Bible. On the other hand, Eagleton is capable of generating an impressive synthesis of Aristotle, Thomas Aquinas, Karl Marx, Walter Benjamin, Ludwig Wittgenstein and Jacques Lacan within his theological formulation of tragic humanism that can be of great use in analysing those facets of human experiences and registers which have so far been the blind spots of secular, liberal methodologies of literary and cultural studies. Lastly, the framework of Eagleton's Catholic theology reconciles tradition with human freedom, mediates between the individual and community. By extension, this political theology intercedes between an individual text and the social, cultural and historical matrix of its production.

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